

A Comparative Study of Business Responsibility and Sustainability Reporting Practices: Evidence from Indian Gas Industry

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Abstract

Since the introduction of NVG (National Voluntary Guidelines) and NGRBC (National Guidelines on Responsible Business Conduct), companies were obligated to adopt the nine principles of responsible business operations and activities included in the both mentioned guidelines as a base. With adaptation of said principles companies are mandated to report about the actions, policies or plans that they undertook in adopting these principles through their BRR (Business Responsibility Report), which is currently updated into BRSR (Business Responsibility and Sustainability Reporting). Though SEBI (Indian Security Exchange Board) has provided a standard format of reporting, companies were having different levels of compliance. Therefore this study aims to examine and compare the Responsibility Reporting practices of companies. Indian companies from Gas Industry (Indraprastha Gas Ltd., Gujarat State Petronet Ltd (GSPL), GAIL (India) Ltd., and Petronet LNG Ltd.) were selected which were continuously part of the top 500 listed companies of NSE in Gas Industry since 2016-17 as business responsibility reporting became mandatory for 500 companies from 1 April 2016. Content analysis was conducted to examine the reporting practices based on the formats provided by SEBI on 4 scales scoring for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23. Findings indicate that only 2 companies, Gujarat State Petronet Ltd. and GAIL (India) Ltd. have adopted all the 9 principles whereas Indraprastha Gas Ltd has adopted 7 and Petronet LNG Ltd. has adopted only 4 principles into their operations or business processes until BRSR adoption, and in respect of overall reporting practice it was found that quantity existed in the practices of companies as they adopted the proposed format but the quality of the information in respect to what was asked as per the format was not provided clearly. For several responses regarding principle's adaptation, in-depth information was required, to which companies only offered evasive or partial answers.

Keywords: Business Responsibility and Sustainability Reporting, National Stock Exchange, Responsible Business Conduct, Sustainability, ESG, SEBI

I. INTRODUCTION

ESG and sustainability reporting started to be buzz words, or it can be said that getting more attention in India, from the past few years since BRR and BRSR (updated BRR) were introduced by MCA and when the market regulator, the SEBI, made them mandatory to disclose for listed companies through SEBI LODER 34 2(f) regulations and respective amendments during different phases between 2011 and 2023. The growing stakeholder demands for completely open and honest disclosures in corporate reporting have compelled enterprises to bolster their disclosure practices on ESG parameters (Varottil, 2023). The Indian Government's MCA (Ministry of Corporate Affairs) released the Guidelines of voluntary implementation for Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives of companies (Voluntary Guidelines on Corporate Social Responsibility) in 2009 was the initial move in extending the idea of business responsibility. Later, in 2011, these Guidelines were updated as NVG. (National Voluntary Guidelines on Social, Environmental, and Economic Responsibilities of Business), which introduced the concept of BRR' that follows with another update and

transforms the guidelines into NGRBC in 2019, including the format of BRSR. This new format of report introduced one new component, i.e., S for sustainability, into the existing business responsibility report, making a huge difference by expanding disclosure from 3 pages to 40 pages with essential and leadership indicators. These guidelines and reporting formats were developed and improved based on India's social, legal and cultural requirements and concerns as well as global legal requirements and best practices related to environment protection, promotion and events. Recent years have seen a substantial overhaul of India's regulatory framework with the adoption of several directives and laws intended to encourage increased sustainability and honest disclosures in corporate reporting. (Goel, 2018). The BRR framework, introduced by SEBI (Securities and Exchange Board of India) in 2012, has made it compulsory for the leading hundred stock exchange listed companies to include a section on their ESG performance in their yearly disclosures (Mathivanan&Kasilingam, 2020). If we take note of the different countries, they also have undertaken similar initiatives. European Union has CSRD framework for corporate sustainability reporting for which mandatory regulation issued that is in force as of January 2023. Similar is the case of US having SEC climate disclosures framework for disclosing climate risk at proposal stage with final rule anticipated in 2023.

The gas industry, being a key contributor to global energy consumption, holds a substantial responsibility towards sustainable development. As society increasingly demands cleaner and more environmentally friendly sources of energy, gas companies face growing pressure to adopt responsible business practices that minimize negative environmental and social impacts. This research paper embarks on a comprehensive exploration of the business responsibility and sustainability reporting practices within the gas industry by focusing on selected companies listed on the National Stock Exchange.

In order to determine how much these selected companies from gas industry are incorporating the nine principles of responsible business conduct which are outlined in the Ministry of Corporate Affairs' National Guidelines of Responsible Business Conduct into their planning, processes, and operations as evidenced by their Business Responsibility Reports or the updated Business Responsibility and Sustainability Reports (hereafter Responsibility Reporting) this comparative study analysed and evaluated the information provided by these companies.

II. PREVIOUS STUDIES

In recent times, there has been a notable surge in the popularity of BRSR, especially with India's corporate landscape changing. Existing research indicates that Indian companies have become increasingly aware of the importance of incorporating non-financial initiatives and sustainability-related disclosures into their reporting practices (Bhatia & Tuli, 2017) (Kulkarni, 2022)(Aspal & Singh, 2020)(Mathivanan & Kasilingam, 2020).

Research on companies' disclosure procedures, content analysis research, and theoretical studies have all been done. The results of these studies paint a mixed picture of the quantity and quality of sustainability reporting among Indian corporations. Although 88% is a rather high average level of disclosure, the quality of these disclosures is considered to be about 80% (Laskar & Maji, 2016). This indicates that while Indian businesses have made headway in embracing sustainability reporting, there is still opportunity for improvement in the breadth and clarity of these disclosures. The several corporate characteristics, such as firm size, industry, profitability, and ownership structure, which may affect a company's inclination to engage in sustainability reporting, have also been the subject of recent studies (Bhatia & Tuli, 2017). Another Study Conducted by (Prusty & Kumar, 2018), found considerable disparities in ESG disclosure standards between and within Public and Private Sector Power Companies. It was also concluded that public and private companies share more information on the social and governance aspects than the environmental aspect.

The literature further indicates that the development of business responsibility and sustainability reporting in India has been shaped by a combination of regulatory interventions and voluntary initiatives. For instance, the NVG'SEERB (National Voluntary Guidelines on Social, Environmental and Economic Responsibilities of Business), introduced by the MCA in 2011, provided a framework for companies to report on their non-

financial performance (Malarvizhi & Yadav, 2008). There were improvements in sustainability reporting and disclosures since BRR has been mandated, business responsibility report had positive impact on disclosure practices as compared the sustainability reporting practices before and after the BR has been mandated (Gupta, 2022).

As we dive in more recent studies on BRSR mandated by SEBI, we find that while the regulatory framework has been established, the existing literature primarily focuses on the overall corporate landscape, with limited attention to the specific practices and approaches adopted by gas industry companies in India in their responsibility reporting, highlighting the need for a focused study in this domain. This research study aimed to contribute to the existing literature by providing a comprehensive and in-depth understanding of the responsibility reporting practices of gas industry companies listed on the National Stock Exchange of India.

III. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Thus following research questions were the primary focus of this study:

1. How much of disclosures have companies made while taking the SEBI provided format as the base?
2. Were there differences in reporting practices of the selected companies?

IV. OBJECTIVE

This study examined and compared the Business Responsibility Reporting practices of selected companies in the gas industry listed on the National Stock Exchange on the basis of given format provided by Security exchange board of India. This format has been provided to the companies to report information on the initiatives or practices they have undertaken to for adopting the provided nine principles mentioned in the NVG and NGRBC.

V. HYPOTHESIS

For comparing the reporting practices of the selected companies a hypothesis was formed-.
H0: There is no significant difference in Reporting Disclosure Index of selected companies.

VI. METHODOLOGY

The intent of this descriptive and analytical study based on secondary data was to examine and compare the responsibility reporting practices of the companies selected from the gas industries as outlined in Table 1. Selected companies were from listed companies of National Stock Exchange (NSE) where companies were grouped as indices i.e. Largecap (Top 100), Midcap (Next 150), and Small cap (Next 250) that covers top 500 listed companies. Therefor gas industry companies falling in Large cap, Mid cap and Small cap were selected. These companies were selected on the basis of market capitalisation as on 31st March 31, 2016, and continuous reporting of BRR since 2016. Selection criteria was made considering the year 2016 as base year, because BRR became mandatory for the top 500 NSE listed companies from April 1, 2016, after the amendment in Rule 34 (2) (f) of the Securities Exchange Board of India Listing Obligation and Disclosure Requirement [SEBI LODR] Regulations 2015. For this study, secondary data was collected from annual reports, Standalone Business responsibility reports, standalone business responsibility and sustainability reports, and websites of the selected companies. The study was carried out for duration of 2016-2023. To do a content analysis and assess the reports, a checklist was developed constructed from SEBI's reporting format and previous research. After score allocation, the Reporting Index was calculated as a percentage of the total score obtained from the total achievable (expected) scores.

Table 1- List of Selected Companies

Company	NSE Index (as on 31 st March 2016)
Indraprastha Gas Ltd.	Mid Cap
GSP Ltd.	Mid Cap
Petronet LNG Ltd.	Large Cap
GAIL (India)	Large Cap

* No gas company fall under small cap companies

VII. CONTENT ANALYSIS

Content analysis, a 75-year-old term, was first used in World War 2 by Harold Lasswell to evaluate enemy propaganda. It has evolved through quantitative studies, propaganda analysis, social scientific studies, computer text analysis, and qualitative challenges in new media. Many authors have described content analysis in their time-dimensional opinions since its inception. Berelson (1952), for instance, defined it as a study approach of describing the communication contents in a methodical, objective, and quantifiable manner. “It is a method for deriving conclusions from messages by methodically and impartially identifying their features” according to Holsti (1968).

Krippendorff (2004, 2e) explained it as “a research technique for making replicable and valid inferences from texts (or other meaningful matter) to the contexts of their use”. This study utilized content analysis using a checklist with 4-point scoring scheme for non-disclosure, disclosure, incomplete or vague disclosure, and disclosure with additional details. Checklist variables were set on the basis of business responsibility reports and business responsibility and sustainability reports format provided by SEBI through SEBI LODER regulations 34(2)(f).

VIII. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Table 2- Implementation Year of BRR and BRSR in Selected Companies

Companies	BRR	BRSR
Indraprastha Gas Ltd	2016-17	2021-22
GSP Ltd	2016-17	2022-23
Petronet LNG Ltd	2012-13	2022-23
GAIL (India)	2012-13	2021-22

Among the selected companies Indraprastha Gas Ltd and GSP Ltd have adopted and publish their BRR in 2016-17 whereas Petronet LNG Ltd and GAIL (India) have adopted it since 2012-13 both groups have adopted it after reporting became mandatory. In case of BRSR Indraprastha and GAIL were early adopters, GSP Ltd. and Petronet LNG Ltd adopted it when it became mandatory to publish BRSR for listed companies as per the circular issued by SEBI.

While reviewing the structure of business responsibility report as provided by SEBI the type of information required to disclose can be divided into objective and subjective. The first 4 sections which are general, financial, other, and BR information are related to objective information as responses are required either in static information or in yes or no responses. The last section principle-wise performance is related to subjective information as detailed information is asked for each principle.

Objective Information- For first four sections selected companies have responded to all the required information as per the BRR format but while responding to the explanation of negative response Indraprastha and Petronet both have provided the footnote instead of following the given format.

Figure 1 - Number of principles for which Policies are formed by the companies

Indraprastha did not have policies for sustainability throughout the product life cycle i.e. principle 2 and stakeholder engagement i.e. principle 4 but claimed to take actions as and when required. But later Indraprastha gas limited and Petronet LNG limited formulated the policies for the rest of all the remaining principles too while upgrading their reporting from BRR to BRSR.

Subjective information

While responding for stakeholder complaints Indraprastha has stated stakeholders include investors employees customers vendors government and local communities but provided details of investors complaints only, it neither stated whether they have received complaints from other stakeholders nor provided any information on stakeholders complaints in 2020-21 as well it has mentioned the procedure of addressing customer complaints but didn't provided the number of complaints received, resolved and pending.

Gujarat Petronet Ltd. discussed about complaint reporting and their settlement structure but didn't provide clear information on receipt of complaints and number of complaints.

In response of incorporating social or environmental concerns risk or opportunities into the product design Indraprastha has explained how their products concerned about environmental and social aspects but didn't mentioned whether their product design has incorporated this concern or not.

For the reduction of resources used throughout the value chain since the previous year, all the selected companies have shown their concern towards reduction and how they are reducing but none of them have mentioned in any rear that how much has been reduced since the previous year.

Indraprastha Gas limited has followed the provided format while reporting on business responsibilities except for the response of explanation regarding the non-formulation of the policies regarding principle 2 and 4.

RDI

The Reporting Disclosure Index was calculated by dividing total score obtained with total achievable (expected) scores.

$$RDI = \frac{\sum \text{Score Obtained}}{\sum \text{Expected Score}} * 100$$

Table 3 Reporting Disclosure Index

	Indraprastha Gas Ltd	Gujarat State Petronet Ltd	Petronet LNG Ltd	GAIL (India) Ltd
2016-17	96.84	98.10	101.90	106.33
2017-18	98.10	98.73	102.53	105.70
2018-19	98.10	100.63	101.27	105.70
2019-20	98.10	100.63	101.27	105.70
2020-21	98.73	100.63	102.53	105.06
2021-22	98.05	100.63	98.73	100.20
2022-23	99.50	101.00	99.60	100.40

Source- Researcher's Computations

While calculating reporting disclosure index, which explains the level of compliance with the provided format of reporting given by the SEBI through the LODR regulations, 100 scores represent full compliance, whereas a score below 100 shows missing information on some aspects in compliance with the format; and score above 100 shows additional information that was provided while complying with the format. In some years RDI was unchanged as all reported Information was same. Table 3 and Fig. 2 shows how company disclosures were moved towards score 100 after updating BRR to BRSR, as companies with a score below

100 were improved after year of BRSR adoption, and companies with scores above 100 also moved to score 100 due to expanded and improved coverage of information in updated BRSR.

Figure 2 Reporting Disclosure Index

As during the study, reporting practices have been analysed through the observation with content analysis and observations have been quantified through the scoring system, parametric test ANOVA could have been used for comparing the reporting practices but one of the major assumptions of the ANOVA is normality of distribution that needs to be followed before applying ANOVA.

Table 4 Test of Normality

	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
DI	.901	28	.013

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Source: Researchers computation generated with IBM SPSS 20

Normality test was conducted, since sample is less than 50, Shapiro-Wilk test followed. The results as shown in Table-4 showed a significant departure from normality with $W(28) = .901, p(sig.) < 0.05$ which shows that data does not follow the normal distribution.

Thus Kruskal-Wallis Test has been used for comparing the reporting practices of the companies.

Table 5- Hypothesis test results of Reporting Practices among the selected companies

Null hypothesis	Test	Sig. value	Decision
There is no significant difference in Reporting Disclosure Index of selected companies.	Independent -Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.001	Reject null hypothesis

Source - Researchers computation generated with IBM SPSS 20

Table-5 shows the hypothesis test summary of Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test conducted to examine the differences of Reporting Practices of selected companies. Significant differences were found with $H(3) = 16.898, p = .001$. The significance value is less than **0.05** therefore the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in responsibility reporting practices of the selected companies has been rejected which interpret that there is significant difference between responsibility reporting practices of the companies.

IX. CONCLUSION

As the study found, businesses are less receptive to voluntary regulatory adoption until such regulations are made necessary. Few businesses actively participate in voluntary adoption to position themselves as early

initiators or active adopters. The structure of BRRs can be divided into objective and subjective information, with objective information requiring responses in general, financial, other, and BR sections. Indraprastha and Petronet provided footnotes instead of BRR format for negative responses, despite lacking sustainability policies and stakeholder engagement principles throughout the product life cycle. They claimed to take necessary actions. Indraprastha has responded to stakeholder complaints, but only provided details of investors' complaints. Gujarat Petronet Ltd. discussed complaint reporting but did not provide information on complaints received, resolved, or pending. Indraprastha has expressed concern about incorporating social and environmental concerns into product design but did not specify how they are incorporating those concerns in product design. All selected companies have shown concern for resource reduction but did not provide details on reductions until it is included in essential indicators of BRSR. These observations show that companies are adopting and responding to the regulation but not exactly up to the information that is been asked to report. This is the reason even after following a given format of reporting all companies reporting practices are not same and hypothesis test revealed significant differences in responsibility reporting practices, rejecting the null hypothesis that there was no significant difference. Thus more clear guidelines and set of instruction is needed to assist the companies to respond to the regulations and related reporting to serve their true objectives and bring some level of harmonized in their responses. BRSR is somewhat fulfilling on those ground of harmonization but efforts are required to make companies more familiarized with BRSR.

X. REFERENCES

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